

Depending on the brand and model, the manufacture and transport of a smartphone produces around 30-60 kg CO₂eq [1-6].

With average use, the energy consumption of a smartphone releases around 2kg of CO₂eq per year [1-6].

35 % of people in Germany have purchased a used smartphone or other IT device in the last two years, with the percentage rising to 55 % among 16-29 years old [7].

Energy saving mode can reduce the smartphone's power consumption by up to 50 % [9].

2,5 years is the average lifespan of a smartphone in Germany [8].

A refurbished smartphone has a 78% lower CO₂-footprint compared to a new purchased one [10].

References:

[1] Sánchez, D., Baur, S.-J., & Eguren, L. (2020). Life cycle assessment of the Fairphone 5. Fraunhofer IZM. https://www.fairphone.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Fairphone5_LCA_Report_2024.pdf

[2] Apple. (2024). iPhone 16 and iPhone 16 Plus | Product Environmental Report. https://www.apple.com/environment/pdf/products/iphone/iphone_16_and_iphone_16_plus_PER_Sept2024.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com

[3] Samsung Electronics. (2024). Galaxy S24. https://www.samsung.com/global/sustainability/media/pdf/Galaxy_S24_Environmental_Report_EN.pdf

[4] XIAOMI CORPORATION. (2021). Product Environmental Report. [https://cdn.cnbj1.fds.api.mi-img.com/staticfile/svnc/2023%E5%B9%B4%E5%8F%AF%E6%8C%81%E7%BB%AD%E5%8F%91%E5%B1%95%E7%BD%91%E7%AB%99/Product%20Environmental%20Report--Xiaomi14%E5%BC%88EN\).pdf](https://cdn.cnbj1.fds.api.mi-img.com/staticfile/svnc/2023%E5%B9%B4%E5%8F%AF%E6%8C%81%E7%BB%AD%E5%8F%91%E5%B1%95%E7%BD%91%E7%AB%99/Product%20Environmental%20Report--Xiaomi14%E5%BC%88EN).pdf)

[5] Schomberg, A., Mostert, C., & Bringezu, S. (2023). Environmental footprints show the savings potential of high reparability through modular smartphone design. Research Square (Research Square). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2724319/v1>

[6] Nothing. (n.d.). Phone (2a). https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0583/0072/7462/files/Phone_2a_Sustainability_Report_250324-de-DE.pdf?v=1719401648

[7] Circular Economy. (2024, October 10). Umfrage des TÜV-Verbands: Gebrauchte Smartphones, Tablets und Laptops erfreuen sich wachsender Beliebtheit. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.umweltwirtschaft.com/news/abfallwirtschaft-und-recycling/Umfrage-des-TueV-Verbands-Gebrauchte-Smartphones-Tablets-und-Laptops-erfreuen-sich-wachsender-Beliebtheit-31060>

[8] Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH. (2024, June 13). Mehr Lebenszeit fürs Handy: Wie wir die Emissionen halbieren könnten. idw - Informationsdienst Wissenschaft e.V. Nachrichten Aus Der Wissenschaft. <https://nachrichten.idw-online.de/2024/06/13/mehr-lebenszeit-fuers-handy-wie-wir-die-emissionen-halbieren-koennten>

[9] Williams, J. (2023, December 1). Power-saving Mode Extends Android Battery Life. DevX. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.devx.com/technology/power-saving-mode-extends-android-battery-life/>

[10] Simic, N. (2024, December 16). Finnish company refurbishes smartphones to cut carbon emissions. European Investment Bank. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.eib.org/en/stories/finland-refurbishing-smartphone-critical-raw-materials>